

Heat Transfer in Solar Water Heaters Pipes

Thermosyphonic Systems

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Abstract

This work introduces the development of formulas for heat transfer in solar water heater pipes to allow calculations of energy losses in pipes.

Solar legislation in Israel requires the installation of solar water heaters in new buildings up to 9 floors from the roof. The legislation from the year 1980 is based on the technology of the late 70s. This publication compares the old types of installation (steel pipes) with the current common practice (2017) in Israel.

Thermosyphonic systems are installed up to 4 floors below the roof, based on old beliefs regarding waste of time waiting for hot water, waste of water and energy losses in long pipes.

This work analyzes the possibility of the installation of thermosyphonic systems on lower floors than the 4th floor under the roof.

The results are energy losses, waste of time waiting for hot water and waste of water, depending on the pipe's length and distance to the apartment.

This publication may be helpful for the techno-economic evaluation of water heating options and the determination of the optimum solutions. It also contains a large number of useful formulas, data and information and can serve as basic material for solar water heaters calculations.

1. Glossary

E	energy [kcal] (not kcal/hr)
kcal	kilo-calorie, energy unit
Q	energy in time [kcal/hr] (not kcal)
SE	Solar Energy
SWH	Solar Water Heater, in this work domestic solar water heater for residential units
U	overall heat transfer coefficient [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
V	water flow [liter/hour]
XLPE	cross-linked Poly-Ethylene
α	thermal conductivity of laminar layer [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
λ	specific thermal conductivity [kcal/m,hr,°C]
ρ	density [kg/liter]

2. Introduction

Solar water heaters must be installed in new buildings in Israel according to the law. Solar water heaters save 5 % of the national electricity generation [9] and are an important component of the Israeli economy and standard of living. The solar law requires solar water heaters for buildings up to 27 meters high, considering energy losses for longer piping. Usually, thermosyphonic installations are up to 4 floors from the roof, and for lower floors, up to 9 floors from the roof, forced circulation systems are applied.

The expression "thermosyphonic" (also "thermosiphonic", also "gravity") means natural circulation between the solar collector and hot water storage tank using the difference of water density at different temperatures.

This publication compares old types of installation (steel pipe) with the current common practice (2017) of installation of solar water heaters in Israel.

Thermosyphonic systems are installed up to 4 floors below roof, based on old beliefs regarding long wait for hot water and energy losses in long pipes.

This work analyzes the possibility of installation of thermosyphonic systems in lower floors than 4th floor under the roof.

The aim of this work is to analyze various parameters related to components of SWH, especially the length of hot water supply pipe.

Publication of "*Energy Balance of Solar Water Heaters: Thermosyphonic Systems*" [8] created a new tool that allowed to make this work.

The results are energy losses, waste of time waiting for hot water and waste of water depending on pipe's length and distance to the apartment.

All conditions are for Israel, so the results do not necessarily apply to other countries.

3. Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as an energy unit. In this work the energy unit is kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal.

Application of kcal instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference indicates immediately the amount of energy in kcal.

Electric energy is expressed in kWh.

1 kWh is 859.85 kcal and 1 kcal is 1.1630 kWh.

4. Heat Transfer

Usually heat transfer is in 3 forms:

- conduction
- convection
- radiation

Both convection and radiation need air space and temperature differences for heat transfer.

In this case, all pipes are insulated (according to national standards) and most of the pipe's length is inside the building. Therefore this work considers conduction only and neglects convection and radiation.

5. Heat Transfer in SWH Pipes

The thermosyphonic system applies insulated pipes for 2 purposes:

- connections between the solar collector and the storage tank
- hot water pipe from the storage tank to the residential unit

The formula developed in this work serves both systems, however each system must be calculated separately because each system operates in different temperatures and may use different types of pipes and insulation.

6. Piping System

Usually SWH hot water piping system includes two concentric pipes:

- Water pipe which is inner pipe for water flow, water-tide holding the water pressure
- Outer pipe for thermal insulation

To develop a formula for heat transfer in two concentric pipes, we can start with the basic formula for conduction heat transfer:

7. Formula for Heat Transfer in Single Pipe

Heat transfer by conduction is determined by Fourier's Law:

Formula 1 - Heat transfer by conduction

$$Q = U * A * \Delta t$$

- Q heat transfer [kcal/hr]
 U overall heat transfer coefficient [kcal/m²,hr,°C]
 A layer's area [m²]
 Δt temperature difference on both sides of the layer [°C]

The calculations are for Δt.

Formula 2 - Calculations of temperature difference

$$\Delta t = Q / (U * A)$$

$$U = \lambda / \delta$$

- λ specific thermal conductivity of the layer material [kcal/m,°C,hr]
 δ thickness of the layer [m]

$$\Delta t = [Q / (\lambda * A)] * \delta$$

To find the formula for the heat transfer through the pipe's wall, we can consider a very thin layer inside the pipe, dr thick, located at radius r from the center of the pipe. The radius "r" is located between the outer radius r_{out} of the pipe and the inner radius r_{in} . In such case the temperature difference Δt of both sides of this very thin layer will be dt .

Formula 3 - Heat transfer in pipe's very thin layer

$$dt = [Q / (\lambda * A)] * dr$$

dr thickness of the very thin layer [m]

$$A = 2 * \pi * r * L$$

$2 * \pi * r$ width of the very thin layer [m]

L length of the very thin layer = 1m

$$dt = [Q / (\lambda * 2 * \pi * r * L)] * dr$$

Formula 4 - Differential equation for very thin layer in pipe

$$dt = [Q / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda)] * dr / r$$

The differential function $a * dx/x$ has solution $a/\ln(x)$ [1], while x is from r_{in} to r_{out} .

Formula 5 - Integration result of the differential equation from r_{in} to r_{out}

$$\Delta t = [Q / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda)] * [\ln(r_{out}) - \ln(r_{in})]$$

The logarithms function $[\ln(a) - \ln(b)]$ equals to $\ln(a/b)$ [2]

$$\ln(r_{out}) - \ln(r_{in}) = \ln(r_{out} / r_{in}) \quad [2]$$

To make the calculations easier, we can replace the radiuses by diameters

$$d = 2 * r$$

$$r_{out} / r_{in} = (2 * r_{out}) / (2 * r_{in}) = d_{out} / d_{in}$$

d_{out} outer diameter of the pipe [m]

d_{in} inner diameter of the pipe [m]

$$\Delta t = Q * \ln(d_{out}/d_{in}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda)$$

$$\Delta t * (2 * \pi * L * \lambda) = Q * \ln(d_{out}/d_{in})$$

Formula 6 - Heat transfer through pipe

$$Q = 2 * \pi * L * \lambda * \Delta t / \ln(d_{out}/d_{in})$$

8. Formula of Heat Transfer through Double Pipe

To consider heat transfer through 2 pipes, we have to combine the thermal resistance of each pipe.

Formula 7 - Combined thermal resistance of 2 concentric pipes

$$R = r_1 + r_2$$

- r₁ thermal resistance of pipe 1 [m²,°C,hr /kcal]
- r₂ thermal resistance of pipe 2 [m²,°C,hr /kcal]
- R combined thermal resistance of all pipes [m²,°C,hr /kcal]

$$r = 1 / U$$

- r thermal resistance of the layer [m²,°C,hr /kcal]
- U thermal conduction of the layer [kcal/m²,°C,hr]

As demonstrated above, it is somehow complicated to determine the area of the layer for pipes, therefore we shall consider combined parameter for thermal conduction and the area, UA:

Coming back to the basic formula for conduction heat transfer

$$Q = U * A * \Delta t$$

$$UA \text{ [kcal/°C,hr]} = U * A$$

Formula 8 - Application of UA parameter

$$Q = UA * \Delta t$$

In the same way we can define combined parameter for thermal resistance and the area, rA:

Formula 9 - Application of rA parameter

$$rA \text{ [}^\circ\text{C,hr/kcal]} = 1 / UA$$

$$Q = UA * \Delta t$$

$$UA = Q / \Delta t$$

$$UA = [2 * \pi * L * \lambda * \Delta t / \ln(d_{out}/d_{in})] / \Delta t$$

$$UA = 2 * \pi * L * \lambda / \ln(d_{out}/d_{in})$$

rA of pipe 1 is:

$$rA1 = 1 / UA1 =$$

$$= 1 / [2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1 / \ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1})]$$

$$= \ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1)$$

$$rA1 = \ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1)$$

and of pipe 2:

$$rA2 = \ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_2)$$

Total RA of all pipes is:

$$RA = rA1 + rA2$$

$$RA = \ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1) + \ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_2)$$

And the thermal conduction of both pipes is:

$$UA = 1 / RA =$$

$$= 1 / \{ [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_2)] \}$$

Formula 10 - UA parameter for 2 concentric pipes

$$UA = 1 / \{ [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_2)] \}$$

9. Thermal Resistance of Laminar Layers

Laminar layer is a very thin layer of media like water or air at immediate proximity to the pipe (inside or outside). This laminar layer adds thermal resistance to the total heat exchange through the pipe.

Formula 11 - Thermal resistance of laminar layer

$$r = 1 / \alpha$$

r thermal resistance [m²°C,hr]

α thermal conductivity of the laminar layer [kcal/m²°C,hr]

9.1. Thermal Resistance of Inside Laminar Layer - Water Side

The inside laminar layer is at the water side. Thermal resistance of the inside laminar layer is r_{in} .

$$r_{in} = 1 / \alpha_{in} \quad [11]$$

α_{in} for water is between 200 and 10,000 kcal/m²°C,hr, depending on the water flow.

Higher is the water flow, higher is the value of α_{in} .

For the circulation pipes between the solar collector and the storage tank with low thermosyphonic water flow this work applies 1,000 kcal/m²°C,hr.

For the hot water pipe supplying hot water from the SWH storage tank to the residential unit with the city water pressure (6 atm), the maximum value of α_{in} will be regarded in this work, which is 10,000 kcal/m²°C,hr.

$$UA_{in} = \alpha_{in} * A_{in}$$

A_{in} heat exchange area, inner side pipe area [m²]

$$A_{in} [m^2] = \pi * d_{in1} * L$$

d_{in1} inside diameter of pipe 1 (hot water pipe)

L pipe length $L = 1$ m

$$UA_{in} = \alpha_{in} * \pi * d_{in1} * L$$

$$r_{Ain} = 1 / UA_{in}$$

Formula 12 - Thermal resistance of the inside laminar layer

$$r_{Ain} = 1 / (\alpha_{in} * \pi * d_{in1} * L)$$

9.2. Thermal Resistance of Outside Laminar Layer - Air Side

The outside laminar layer is at the air side. Thermal resistance of the outside laminar layer is r_{out} . Its values may be found in [4].

$$r_{out} = 1 / \alpha_{out}$$

$$UA_{out} = \alpha_{out} * A_{out}$$

A_{out} heat exchange area, outer side area [m²]

$$A_{out} [m^2] = \pi * d_{out2} * L$$

d_{out2} outside diameter of pipe 2 (insulation)

L pipe length $L = 1$ m

$$UA_{out} = \alpha_{out} * \pi * d_{out2} * L$$

$$r_{Aout} = 1 / UA_{out}$$

Formula 13 - Thermal resistance of the outside laminar layer

$$r_{Aout} = 1 / [\alpha_{out} * \pi * d_{out2} * L]$$

10. Total Thermal Resistance of Two Pipes and Laminar Layers

Formula 14 - Total thermal resistance of two pipes and laminar layers

$$RA = r_{Ain} + r_{A1} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout}$$

All r elements were calculated before and may be entered into the formula:

$$RA = [1 / (\alpha_{in} * \pi * d_{in1} * L)] + [\ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_1)] + \\ + \ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \pi * L * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * \pi * d_{out2} * L)]$$

Every component of R has parameters π and L, which allows extracting them to the beginning of the equation:

$$RA = \{ 1 / (\pi * L) \} * \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + \\ + [\ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Total UA is:

$$UA = 1 / RA$$

$$UA = 1 / \{ 1 / (\pi * L) \} * \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

$$UA = (\pi * L) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

$$Q = UA * \Delta t$$

Formula 15 - Final formula for heat transfer of multi-layer pipe

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Each component of the above formula in square parentheses is the thermal resistance of a single layer. The sum of all resistance components is Σr . In the above case:

Formula 16 - Sum of thermal resistance components

$$\Sigma r = \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Formula 17 - Heat transfer considering the sum of thermal resistance components

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \Sigma r$$

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi / \Sigma r)$$

Table 1 - Resistance and conductivity of laminar layers

		Thermosyphonic circulation pipes	Forced circulation	Hot water supply pipe
r_{in} water	m ² °C,hr/kcal	0.0010	0.0002	0.0001
r_{out} air	m ² °C,hr/kcal	0.0465	0.1512	0.1512
α_{in} water	kcal/m ² °C,hr	1,000	5,000	10,000
α_{out} air	kcal/m ² °C,hr	21.50	6.61	6.61

11. Sleeve Instead of Insulation

In many cases (in Israel) cheap Poly-Ethylene pipe is used as a sleeve on hot water pipe from solar water heater, instead of insulation.

There is an air gap between the water pipe and the sleeve.

The sum of thermal resistance of both pipes and all laminar layers is as follows:

Formula 18 - Thermal resistance of water pipe, sleeve and laminar layers

$$RA = r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1} + r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2}$$

$r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1}$ are related to the water pipe

$r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2}$ are related to the sleeve

r_{A1} rA of water pipe

r_{A2} rA of sleeve

r_{Ainx}, r_{Aoutx} rA of laminar layers

Formula 19 - Heat transfer through water pipe and sleeve with air gap

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in1} * d_{in1})] + [\ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + \\ + [1 / (\alpha_{out1} * d_{out1})] + [1 / (\alpha_{in2} * d_{in2})] \\ + [\ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Index 1 is related to the water pipe, and index 2 is related to the sleeve.

α_{out1} and α_{in2} are for air trapped between the water pipe and the sleeve.

12. Double Sleeve Instead of Insulation

Double sleeve of cheap Polyethylene pipe may be cheaper than the thermal insulation.

Analysis of such a system will allow comparison with thermal insulation.

Formula 20 - Thermal resistance of the water pipe, both sleeves and all laminar layers

$$RA = r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1} + r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2} + r_{Ain3} + r_{A3} + r_{Aout3}$$

$r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1}$ are related to the water pipe

$r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2}$ are related to the inner sleeve

$r_{Ain3} + r_{A3} + r_{Aout3}$ are related to the outer sleeve

Formula 21 - Heat transfer through water pipe and double sleeve with air gap

$$\begin{aligned} Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ & [1 / (\alpha_{in1} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + \\ & + [1 / (\alpha_{out1} * d_{out1})] + [1 / (\alpha_{in2} * d_{in2})] \\ & + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] + [1 / (\alpha_{in3} * d_{in2})] \\ & + [\text{Ln}(d_{out3}/d_{in3}) / (2 * \lambda_3)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out3})] \} \end{aligned}$$

Index 1 is related to the water pipe, index 2 is related to the inner sleeve and index 3 is related to the outer sleeve.

α_{out1} , α_{in2} , α_{out2} and α_{in3} are for air trapped between the pipes.

13. Sum of Thermal Resistance in Pipe's Assembly

All the above formulas for heat transfer in pipe or pipes have similar structure:

Formula 22 - Heat transfer and thermal resistance of pipe's assembly

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [r1] + [r2] + \dots + [r_n] \}$$

Q	heat transfer if pipe's assembly [kcal/hr]
L	pipe's length [m]
Δt	temperature difference between inside and outside of the pipe's assembly [°C]
r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n	thermal resistance of single layer of the pipe's assembly [m°C,hr/kcal]

$$R = \Sigma r = [r1] + [r2] + \dots + [r_n]$$

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \Sigma r$$

Formula 23 - Application of $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi/\Sigma r)$$

$(\pi/\Sigma r)$ will be further called " $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter" [kcal/m°C,hr].

14. Hot Water Pipe Material

Two kinds of hot water pipes' material will be considered:

- steel pipe, as in late 70s
- High-Density Crosslinked Polyethylene (XLPE), currently used in Israel

The Israeli manufacturer of High-Density Crosslinked Polyethylene (XLPE) pipes is Pexgol [5].

Table 2 - Properties of steel pipe

density	7.85	g/cm ³
density	7,850	kg/m ³
c	0.5	kJ/kg°C
kJ to kcal	0.23885	kJ/kcal
c	0.12	kcal/kg°C
cv	937	kcal/m ³ °C
λ	54	W/m°C
Wh to kcal	0.85985	Wh/kcal
λ	46	kcal/m°C ,hr

Table 3 - Properties of Pexgol pipes

		Unit	Reference
Max service temperature	110	°C	[4]
Specific heat	2.3	kJ/kg,°C	[4]
kJ to kcal	0.2388459	kJ/kcal	DOE
Specific heat	0.55	kcal/kg,°C	
Specific thermal conductivity	0.35	W/m,°C	[4]
kWh to kcal	859.85	kWh/kcal	DOE
Specific thermal conductivity	0.301	kcal/hr,m,°C	

Table 4 - Properties of Anavid Vidoflex HT thermal insulation

Max service temperature	150	°C	[6]
Density	85	kg/m ³	[6]
Specific heat	2.0000	kJ/kg,°C	[7]
kJ to kcal	0.2388	kJ/kcal	
Specific heat	0.4777	kcal/kg,°C	
Specific thermal conductivity	0.0388	W/m,°C	[6]
Wh to kcal	0.8598	Wh/kcal	DOE
Specific thermal conductivity	0.0334	kcal/hr,m,°C	

15. Diameter of Hot Water Supply Pipe

The diameter of the hot water supply pipe applied in this work is 1/2" steel pipe and its plastic equivalent is 16 mm OD.

Table 5 - Diameter of hot water supply pipe

		Plastic	Steel
Material		XLPE	St37
Dia Out	mm	16	21.25
Thickness	mm	2.2	2.35
Dia In	mm	11.6	16.55

The main component restricting water flow is the aerator in shower head or in tap. Usually the water flow in the tap or shower is 5 liters per minute.

Table 6 - Water flow

		Steel	Plastic
Dia In	m	0.01655	0.01160
cross section	m ²	0.00022	0.00011
water flow @5L/min	m/s	0.39	0.79
example length	m	50	50
pressure losses	bar	0.41	0.47

Pressure drop was calculated using the pressure drop online calculator [10].

In thermosyphonic installations hot water supply pipe is under city water pressure, usually 6 bar. Pressure drop of 0.4-0.5 bar for 50 meters long pipe is not critical for 6 bar pipe's pressure.

16. Pipes Insulation

According to the Israeli Standard [3] pipes' insulation must have thermal conductivity lower than 0.04 W/m°C and minimum thickness of 13 mm inside the building or 19 mm outside the building.

The Israeli manufacturer of pipe insulation is Anavid [6].

High temperature insulation is Anavid Vidoflex HT [6] EPDM foam.

Table 7 - Pipe insulation for circulation pipes (outside)

		plastic pipe	steel pipe
Water pipe dia out	mm	16.00	21.25
Insulation dia in	mm	16.00	21.25
Insulation dia in	m	0.016	0.021
Thickness	mm	20	20
Insulation dia out	mm	56.00	61.25
Insulation dia out	m	0.056	0.061

Table 8 - Pipe insulation for hot water supply pipe (inside)

		plastic pipe	steel pipe
Water pipe dia out	mm	16.00	21.25
Insulation dia in	mm	16.00	21.25
Insulation dia in	m	0.016	0.021
Thickness	mm	13	13
Insulation dia out	mm	42.00	47.25
Insulation dia out	m	0.042	0.047

17. Heat Transfer in Circulation Pipe Located Outside

In this section the calculations are per 1 meter length of the circulation pipe located outside.

The relevant heat transfer formula is:

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

$$\Sigma r = \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Application of $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter:

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi/\Sigma r)$$

Table 9 - Input values: Heat transfer in steel circulation pipes

L	1	m
α_{in}	1,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.017	m
dout1	0.021	m
λ_1	46	kcal/m°°C,hr
Din2	0.021	m
dout2	0.061	m
λ_2	0.033	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 10 - Input values: Heat transfer in Pexgol circulation pipes

L	1	m
α_{in}	1,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.012	m
dout1	0.016	m
λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
din2	0.016	m
dout2	0.056	m
λ_2	0.033	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21	kcal/m ² °C,hr

The following tables indicate the contribution of each thermal resistance element to the total thermal resistance.

Table 11 - Steel circulation pipe resistance elements located outside

Element	Formula	Resistance	unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)]$	0.06	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.4%
Steel pipe	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.00	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Insulation	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	15.87	m°°C,hr/kcal	95.1%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)]$	0.76	m°°C,hr/kcal	4.6%
Σr	4	16.69	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Chart 1 - Steel pipe resistance elements

Table 12 - Pexgol XLPE pipe resistance elements

Element	Formula	Resistance	unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})]$	0.09	m°C,hr/kcal	0.4%
XLPE pipe	$[\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°C,hr/kcal	2.6%
Insulation	$[\text{Ln}(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	18.78	m°C,hr/kcal	92.8%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})]$	0.83	m°C,hr/kcal	4.1%
Σr	4	20.23	m°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Chart 2 - XLPE pipe resistance elements

Table 13 - Steel and XLPE circulation pipes resistance elements

Element	Steel	XLPE	Δ
Inside laminar layer	0.06	0.09	43%
Water pipe	0.00	0.53	19749%
Insulation	15.87	18.78	18%
Outside laminar layer	0.76	0.83	9%
Σr	16.69	20.23	21%

Table 14 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for circulation pipe

		Steel	XLPE
Σr	m°C,hr/kcal	16.69	20.23
$\pi/\Sigma r$	kcal/°C,hr	0.188	0.155

Formula for heat transfer in pipe:

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi/\Sigma r)$$

Formula 24 - Heat transfer of 1 meter steel circulation pipe

$$Q = 0.188 \text{ [kcal/°C,hr]} * \Delta t$$

Formula 25 - Heat transfer of 1 meter XLPE circulation pipe

$$Q = 0.155 \text{ [kcal/°C,hr]} * \Delta t$$

Δt is temperature difference between the water inside pipe and outside air
Both temperatures are determined for every month in publication [8].

18. Hot Water Supply Pipe

Hot water supply pipe is the pipe from SWH storage tank to the taps of the residential units. This pipe is in most cases in Israel under city water pressure. In some remote villages a "special tank" is used, located above the SWH, breaking the city water pressure and supplying the cold water and the hot water with gravity

pressure only. This work disregards installations with "special tank" and the calculations are related to the hot water supply pipe under the city water pressure, which is a conservative assumption, reducing the thermal resistance of the water laminar layer in the water pipe.

On the long way from the storage tank to the residential unit, the hot water supply pipe has a few parts:

- outside, requiring 19 mm thermal insulation [3]
- inside the building, requiring 13 mm thermal insulation [3]
- in residential unit, considering its air temperature in the winter, like 18 °C.

The single floor gross height in residential buildings in Israel is 3 meters, 2.5-2.7 meters net height of rooms. It is a common opinion since the late 70's that the thermosyphonic SWH is not effective for more than 4 floors distance from roof. 4 floors distance from roof results in 12 m of the pipe's length. In addition, it must be added about 4 meters for the segments on the roof and in the residential unit.

Formula 26 - Length of hot water supply pipe

$$L = 4 \text{ [m]} + nFL * 3$$

L	pipe's length [m]
4 [m]	estimation of pipe's length on the roof and in the residential unit
nFL	number of floors between the residential unit and the roof
3	gross height of each floor = 3 m

19. Heat Transfer in Hot Water Supply Pipe Located Outside

According to the Israeli Standard [3] thermal insulation of pipes inside a building must be at least 19 mm. Israeli manufacturer of thermal insulation for hot water pipes supplies EPDM foam 20 mm thick. EPDM is a perfect material for external use exposed to solar radiation.

Table 15 - Input data for heat transfer calculations of steel hot water supply pipe located outside

L	1	m
α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.017	m
dout1	0.021	m
λ_1	46	Kcal/m°°C,hr
din2	0.021	m
dout2	0.061	m
λ_2	0.033	Kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21.5	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 16 - Thermal resistance of steel hot water supply pipe located outside

Element	Formula	Resistance	unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)]$	0.01	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Steel pipe	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.00	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Insulation	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	15.87	m°°C,hr/kcal	95.4%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)]$	0.76	m°°C,hr/kcal	4.6%
Σr	4	16.63	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Table 17 - Input data for heat transfer of XLPE hot water supply pipe located outside

L	1	m
α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.012	m
dout1	0.016	m
λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
din2	0.016	m
dout2	0.056	m
λ_2	0.033	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21.5	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 18 - Thermal resistance of XLPE hot water supply pipe located outside

Element	Formula	Resistance	unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)]$	0.01	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Steel pipe	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°°C,hr/kcal	2.7%
Insulation	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	18.78	m°°C,hr/kcal	93.2%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)]$	0.83	m°°C,hr/kcal	4.1%
Σr	4	20.15	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Table 19 - Thermal resistance of steel and XLPE hot water supply pipes located outside

Element	Steel	XLPE	Δ
Inside laminar layer	0.01	0.01	43%
Water pipe	0.00	0.53	19749%
Insulation	15.87	18.78	18%
Outside laminar layer	0.76	0.83	9%
Σr	16.63	20.15	21%

Table 20 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for hot water supply pipe located outside

		Steel	XLPE
Σr	m°C,hr/kcal	16.63	20.15
$\pi/\Sigma r$	kcal/°C,hr	0.189	0.156

20. Heat Transfer in Hot Water Supply Pipe Located Inside

According to the Israeli Standard [3] thermal insulation of pipes inside a building must be at least 13 mm.

The pipes and insulation diameters are detailed in Table "*Pipe insulation for hot water pipe (inside)*".

Table 21 - Input values: Heat transfer in steel hot water supply pipe located inside

L	1	m
α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.017	m
dout1	0.021	m
λ_1	46	kcal/m°C,hr
din2	0.021	m
dout2	0.047	m
λ_2	0.033	kcal/m°C,hr
α_{out}	6.614	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 22 - Input values: Heat transfer in XLPE hot water supply pipe located inside

L	1	m
α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
din1	0.012	m
dout1	0.016	m
λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
din2	0.016	m
dout2	0.042	m
λ_2	0.033	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	6.614	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 23 - Steel pipe resistance elements – hot water supply pipe

Element	Formula	Resistance	Unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)]$	0.01	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Steel pipe	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.00	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Insulation	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	11.98	m°°C,hr/kcal	78.9%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)]$	3.20	m°°C,hr/kcal	21.1%
Σr	4	15.18	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Table 24 - XLPE pipe resistance elements – hot water supply pipe

Element	Formula	Resistance	Unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)]$	0.01	m°°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
XLPE pipe	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°°C,hr/kcal	2.9%
Insulation	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	14.46	m°°C,hr/kcal	77.7%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)]$	3.60	m°°C,hr/kcal	19.3%
Σr	4	18.61	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Chart 3 - XLPE pipe resistance elements – hot water supply pipe

Table 25 - Steel and XLPE hot water supply pipes resistance elements

Element	Steel	XLPE	Δ
Inside laminar layer	0.01	0.01	43%
Water pipe	0.00	0.53	19749%
Insulation	11.98	14.46	21%
Outside laminar layer	3.20	3.60	13%
Σr	15.18	18.61	23%

Table 26 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for hot water supply pipe located inside

		Steel	XLPE
Σr	m°C,hr/kcal	15.18	18.61
$\pi/\Sigma r$	kcal/m°C,hr	0.207	0.169

Formula for heat transfer in pipe:

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi/\Sigma r)$$

Formula 27 - Heat transfer of 1 meter steel hot water supply pipe

$$Q = 0.207 \text{ [kcal/°C,hr]} * \Delta t$$

Formula 28 - Heat transfer of 1 meter XLPE hot water supply pipe

$$Q = 0.169 \text{ [kcal/°C,hr]} * \Delta t$$

21. Energy for Replacement of Cold Water in Pipes

These losses are labeled in tables as:

EW - Energy in Water Losses

$$EW = m * c * \Delta t$$

m mass of water in 1 meter long pipe [kg]

Δt difference between the initial water temperature (city water temperature) and the water temperature in the pipe (circulation water temperature, hot water supply temperature) [°C]

Table 27 - Input data for calculations

		Steel	XLPE
L	cm	100	100
din1	cm	1.66	1.16
Volume	cm ³	215.12	105.68
Volume	Liter	0.22	0.11

22. Initial Heating of Pipe and Insulation Mass

By the end of the day the circulation will stop and all energy of circulation pipes mass will be lost. Also the energy of hot supply pipe mass left unused will be lost. These energy losses are labeled in tables as CircM and SupM.

Following formula is from publication [8]:

$$E = m * c * \Delta t \quad [8]$$

Δt difference between the initial temperature and the final temperature of pipes [°C]

In this case the initial temperature is the month average ambient air temperature

Table 28 - Input values: Initial heating of 1 meter of circulation pipe and insulation mass

		Steel	Pexgol
Length	cm	100	100
din1	cm	1.66	1.16
dout1	cm	2.13	1.60
din2	cm	2.13	1.60
dout2	cm	6.13	5.60
Volume pipe	cm ³	140	95
density pipe	g/cm ³	7.85	0.94
weight pipe	g	1,095	89
weight pipe	kg	1.1	0.1
C pipe	kcal/kg, °C	0.12	0.55
E pipe	kcal/°C	0.13	0.05
Volume insulation	cm ³	2,592	2,262
Density insulation	g/cm ³	0.085	0.085
weight insulation	g	220	192
weight insulation	kg	0.22	0.19
C insulation	kcal/kg, °C	0.48	0.48
E insulation	kcal/°C	0.11	0.09
ΣE	kcal/°C	0.24	0.14

Table 29 - Input values: Initial heating of 1 meter of hot water supply pipe and insulation mass

		Steel	Pexgol
Length	cm	100	100
din1	cm	1.66	1.16
dout1	cm	2.13	1.60
din2	cm	2.13	1.60
dout2	cm	4.73	4.20
Volume pipe	cm ³	140	95
density pipe	g/cm ³	7.85	0.94
weight pipe	g	1,095	89
weight pipe	kg	1.1	0.1
c pipe	kcal/kg, °C	0.12	0.55
E pipe	kcal/°C	0.13	0.05
Volume insulation	cm ³	1,399	1,184
density insulation	g/cm ³	0.085	0.085
weight insulation	g	119	101
weight insulation	kg	0.12	0.10
c insulation	kcal/kg, °C	0.48	0.48
E insulation	kcal/°C	0.06	0.05
ΣE	kcal/°C	0.19	0.10

23. Waste of Time Waiting for Hot Water

Waste of time waiting for hot water has 2 components

- Time for replacement of cold water in the pipe with hot water
- Time to heat at least half of the pipe's mass to 37°C

Time to heat the pipes mass depends on the hot water temperature. Higher is the water temperature faster is the heating process.

Formula 29 - Waste of time waiting for hot water

$$T = T_{\text{water}} + T_{\text{pipe}}$$

T Waste of time waiting for hot water [sec]
 T_{water} Time for replacement of cold water in the pipe with hot water [sec]
 T_{pipe} Time to heat at least half of the pipe's mass to 37°C [sec]

Table 30 - Time for replacement of cold water for 1/2" steel pipe and 16 mm OD plastic pipe

		Steel	XLPE	Δ
Hot water flow	L/sec	0.08	0.08	
Volume	Liter	0.22	0.11	
Time	seconds	2.6	1.3	51%

Formula 30 - Energy for heating hot water supply pipe mass

$$E_p = E_w$$

$$E_p = m_p * c_p * \Delta t_p$$

E_p energy required to heat the pipe to 37°C [kcal]
 m_p pipe mass [kg]
 c_p specific heat of pipe [kcal/kg,°C]
 Δt_p temperature difference of the pipe between 37°C and T_{out} [°C]

$$\Delta t_p = 37^\circ\text{C} - T_{\text{out}}$$

$$E_w = m_w * T_w * c_w * \Delta t_w$$

E_w energy of water [kcal]
 m_w water flow = 5 liters/minute
 T_w time of water flow to reach the required amount of energy
 c_w specific heat of water = 1 [kcal/kg,°C]

Δt_w temperature difference between water temperature and pipe temperature [°C]

Table 31 - mc of pipe for 1/2" steel pipe and 16 mm OD plastic pipe

		Steel	Pexgol
Weight of pipe	kg	1.10	0.09
c pipe	kcal/kg,°C	0.12	0.55
mc	kcal/°C	0.13	0.05

Initial water temperature in hot water supply pipe is city water temperature, T_c .
Time is calculated till comfortable temperature starts, which is 37°C.

Table 32 - Energy for heating 1 meter of steel pipe's mass

Month	T_c °C	Δ to 37°C °C	Energy kcal/meter
1	11.4	25.6	3.4
2	10.3	26.7	3.5
3	13.5	23.5	3.1
4	17.8	19.2	2.5
5	21.7	15.3	2.0
6	23.9	13.1	1.7
7	25.3	11.7	1.5
8	26.1	10.9	1.4
9	23.7	13.3	1.7
10	22.9	14.1	1.8
11	16.7	20.3	2.7
12	14.1	22.9	3.0

Table 33 - Energy for heating 1 meter of plastic pipe's mass

Month	T_c °C	Δ to 37°C °C	Energy kcal/meter
1	11.4	25.6	1.3
2	10.3	26.7	1.3
3	13.5	23.5	1.2
4	17.8	19.2	0.9
5	21.7	15.3	0.7
6	23.9	13.1	0.6
7	25.3	11.7	0.6
8	26.1	10.9	0.5
9	23.7	13.3	0.7
10	22.9	14.1	0.7
11	16.7	20.3	1.0
12	14.1	22.9	1.1

Table 34 - Time to heat steel pipe's mass

Month	Tsup °C	Water Liters	Pipe Mass seconds
1	39.4	0.06	0.7
2	42.2	0.05	0.7
3	45.3	0.05	0.6
4	49.1	0.04	0.5
5	52.2	0.03	0.4
6	54.0	0.03	0.3
7	54.7	0.03	0.3
8	55.9	0.02	0.3
9	54.7	0.03	0.3
10	51.9	0.03	0.4
11	45.4	0.05	0.6
12	40.7	0.06	0.7

Table 35 - Time to heat plastic pipe's mass

Month	Tsup °C	Water Liters	Tpipe seconds
1	39.4	0.02	0.3
2	42.2	0.02	0.2
3	45.3	0.02	0.2
4	49.1	0.02	0.2
5	52.2	0.01	0.1
6	54.0	0.01	0.1
7	54.7	0.01	0.1
8	55.9	0.01	0.1
9	54.7	0.01	0.1
10	51.9	0.01	0.1
11	45.4	0.02	0.2
12	40.7	0.02	0.3

Table 36 - Total time waiting for hot water in January per 1 meter of supply pipe

		Steel	XLPE	Δ
Time water	seconds	2.6	1.3	51%
Time pipe mass January	seconds	0.7	0.3	
Time total January	seconds	3.3	1.5	53%

24. Waste of Water

Waste of water depends on time waiting for hot water as calculated in the previous section.

Table 37 - Waste of water for 1/2" steel pipe and 16 mm OD plastic pipe

		Steel	XLPE	Δ
Water only	m3/d	0.00022	0.00011	
Water only	m3/y	0.07852	0.038574	
Pipe mass only January	m3/d	0.00006	0.00002	
Pipe mass only January	m3/y	0.02272	0.008536	
Total January	m3/d	0.00028	0.00013	
Total January	m3/y	0.10124	0.04711	53%

Plastic pipe saves about 50% of water for hot water supply.

25. Results of Calculations

Table 38 - Waste of time, waste of water and need for backup with floors for 1/2" steel pipe and 16 mm OD plastic pipe

		Steel	Plastic	Steel	Plastic	Steel	Plastic
		January	January				
Floor from roof	pipe length	wait for hot water	wait for hot water	waste of water	waste of water	backup	backup
	m	seconds	seconds	m3/y	m3/y	kWh/y	kWh/y
1	7	23	11	0.7	0.3	304	288
2	10	33	15	1.0	0.5	313	293
3	13	43	20	1.3	0.6	321	298
4	16	53	25	1.6	0.7	329	303
5	19	63	29	1.9	0.9	338	308
6	22	73	34	2.2	1.0	346	313
7	25	83	38	2.5	1.2	355	318
8	28	92	43	2.8	1.3	363	323
9	31	102	48	3.1	1.5	372	328
10	34	112	52	3.4	1.6	380	333
11	37	122	57	3.7	1.7	389	338
12	40	132	62	4.0	1.9	397	343
13	43	142	66	4.3	2.0	406	348
14	46	152	71	4.6	2.2	414	353
15	49	162	75	4.9	2.3	423	358
16	52	172	80	5.2	2.4	431	363
17	55	182	85	5.5	2.6	439	368
18	58	191	89	5.8	2.7	448	373
19	61	201	94	6.1	2.9	456	378
20	64	211	98	6.4	3.0	465	383
21	67	221	103	6.7	3.1	473	388
22	70	231	108	7.0	3.3	482	393
23	73	241	112	7.3	3.4	490	399
24	76	251	117	7.6	3.6	499	404
25	79	261	122	7.9	3.7	507	409
26	82	271	126	8.2	3.8	516	414
27	85	281	131	8.5	4.0	524	419
28	88	290	135	8.8	4.1	533	424
29	91	300	140	9.1	4.3	541	429
30	94	310	145	9.4	4.4	549	434
31	97	320	149	9.7	4.5	558	439
32	100	330	154	10.0	4.7	566	444
33	103	340	158	10.3	4.8	575	449
34	106	350	163	10.6	5.0	583	454
35	109	360	168	10.9	5.1	592	459
36	112	370	172	11.2	5.2	600	464
37	115	380	177	11.5	5.4	609	469
38	118	389	182	11.8	5.5	617	474
39	121	399	186	12.1	5.7	626	479
40	124	409	191	12.4	5.8	634	484

26. Analysis of Results

Following table compares the results for steel pipe and plastic pipe.

Solar legislation in Israel was based on common practice in late 70s. The common practice then was installation of thermosyphonic systems up to 4 floors from roof.

Table 39 - Results for steel pipe and plastic pipe

	Value	Unit	Floors Steel	Floors Plastic
Waste of time	53	seconds	4	10
Waste of water	1.6	m ³ /y	4	10
Backup	329	kWh/y	4	9

The above table shows that modern technology allows installation of thermosyphonic systems up to 10 floors under roof with the same functionality and effectiveness as steel pipes systems used in late 70's, at the time of the beginning of the solar law.

Need for backup for 10 floors plastic pipes system is not equivalent to 4 floors steel pipes system, but the difference is economic only and not functional, requiring addition of 5 kWh/year for backup (about 0.50 USD per year).

27. References

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